

FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING WITH IT TECHNOLOGIES IN THE FIELD OF AGRICULTURE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7298476>

Annotatsiya: This article discusses the methods, types and results of using new information technologies to improve the skills of teaching students English. The information presented in this article is based on the analysis of new lessons learned using several new information technologies.

Kalit so'zlar: Traditional method, motivational potential, IT - information and communication technologies, agriculture, multimedia.

Kirish: The world of the newest information technologies occupies an increasing place in our lives. Computer technologies are becoming an integral part of modern culture, including in the field of education. It is thanks to computer technology that the interest of students in the subject increases significantly, and mental activity is activated.

In the present time, there is an active process of informatization in the field of education, which involves the intensive introduction and application of new information technologies, the use of all means of communication, which enable the formation and intellectual development of creative personality, good orientation in the information space, ready for self-development and application of ethical knowledge and future professional skills.

Our task is for the convenience of using this material by students and teachers, to combine all this as much as possible within the framework of one program. If these are large multimedia programs, then describe by topic what grammatical, lexical or phonetic material can be found in this program, what exercises this product provides. If these are films, indicate possible ways of working with the film and attribute it to a specific lexical topic. If these are various tests (lexical, grammar, listening, video tests), then make a database of tests with the ability to track the results of work on them. As a result: the inclusion and systematization of all possible textual, graphic, audio-video information useful for studying various aspects of a foreign language, both practical and theoretical, will help the teacher reduce the time to prepare for the lesson, while using the advantages of multimedia technologies, and the student, independently increase the level of knowledge of a foreign language by performing exercises, tests and lessons. "Linguist" consists of eight main sections: "Vocabulary", "Grammar", "Phonetics", "Theory", "Internet", "Programs", "Testing", "Multimedia programs". Each of the sections can be supplemented as training material or orders from teachers

arrive. So let's take a closer look at each section.

- "Программы", раздел включает в себя набор бесплатных программ, распространяемых во всемирной сети Интернет, можно найти электронные учебники, с комментариями на русском языке, посвященных обучению иностранному языку.

- "Multimedia programs", at the moment there is a large selection of specialized, professional, multimedia products on the market dedicated to teaching a foreign language. Not every teacher will find comprehensive information about the product of interest to him. The section provides information on the content of the multimedia program: lesson topics, types of exercises used, grammatical material used, lexical base of lessons, video, audio materials.

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